

Firm Attributes and Earnings Quality Among Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined firm characteristics and earnings quality among non-financial companies listed in the Nigerian Exchange Group. Thirty (30) selected non-financial firms were selected through simple convenient sampling technique over a period of six (6) years (2016 – 2021). The model specification captured earnings quality (EQ) as the dependent variable while leverage, firm size, profit and firm age were the independent variables. Both managerial ownership and board financial expertise were control variables. The study employed convenient non-probability sampling method to collect secondary data using the panel data design, descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) estimation technique was conducted alongside various tests with the aid of E-Views 7.0. The study found that leverage, firm size, profitability, and firm age exhibit insignificant impact on earnings quality, however with differing nature of relationship. Based on the result, the study concludes that firm attributes has a weak impact on earnings quality among listed companies in Nigeria. Other attributes that could possibly impact on earnings quality such as corporate governance etc. should be undertaken.

Keywords: Firm characteristics, Earning quality, Firm size, Firm age, Profit, Non-financial companies, Nigerian Stock Exchange Group

Word count: 172

Introduction

The occurrence of financial scandals in major corporations such as World Com and Xerox

aroused enquiry into the quality of financial information upon which users make relevant decisions. According to Shehu (2012), the relevance of financial information is to the extent it can influence decisions makers to form predictions about the outcomes of present event or to confirm or correct prior expectations. Also, the decision useful orientation is predicated on providing quality financial reporting information and one important part of financial reports is earnings quality. Earnings quality can be conceptualized in two ways: the accounting; and the market perspectives. In the former, it is the ability of earnings in the current to predict earnings in the future year (Richardson, 2003). According to Cohen (2003), it is the ability of earnings in the current year to predict future operating cash flow. In the latter, earnings quality should be able to affect the company equity in the Stock market. (K. Chan, L. Chan, Jegadeesh & Lakonishck, 2006). Earnings quality is important because it serves as a variable to assess valuation-relevant information from earnings pattern, contracting decisions (i.e. decisions relating to corporate governance practice), as a feedback mechanism to standard setters and for investment decision making by potential investors. Also, investors need quality financial information in order to reduce information asymmetry.

Giving that earnings quality is pivotal, specifically to investors as it helps reduces information asymmetry, amidst other importance, one important aspect of enquiry that has elicited the views of researchers is the determinants of earnings quality among corporate entities. For instance, Mohammed, Ahmad and Omran (n.d.) classified these determinants into firm characteristics; financial reporting practices; governance and control; auditors; and equity market incentives while Olaoye and Adewumi (2020) classified it into two groups: the innate; and reporting resources. Although investigating and modelling the determinants of earnings quality using the aforementioned classified determinants become germane in any attempt at simulating effective scenarios from which quality financial report could be evaluated and guided on a sustainable path, however this study focuses on firms attributes. According to Hassan and Farouk (2014), firms' specific characteristics play an astute role in restraining managers from manipulating accounting figures which eventually enhance earnings quality. Also, Ibrahim (2016) posits that firms attributes determine the way in which corporate entities are run by managers, they influences the desire of managers to either engage in earnings management practices or not.

The determinants of earnings management has gained dominance in literature unlike earnings quality (Bassiouny, Soliman & Ragab, 2016; Shadrach & Yakura, 2021; Shaikh, Shaique & Nasir, 2019; Hamzah, Gozali & Khamisah, 2022; Hoang & Nguyen, 2018; Lingyun, Gumende & Enhua, 2017;). Earnings quality using the Nigerian data is still in its

infancy, and giving that quality accounting environment differ across countries, applying the retinue of findings from international perspectives will affect policy implication. Also, one of the purposes of financial information is to support capital market participants in making judgments and decisions. According to Yasser (2015), the aspects of capital market which earnings quality is expected to affect are: the cost of equity capital, which is considered to be a summary indicator of investors' resource allocation decisions; information asymmetry and; analysts' information environment. Thus, understanding the determinants of earnings quality could shed light on the implications a healthy financial report could have on stock market efficiency and vice versa. Therefore, this study is motivated to investigate the determinants of earnings quality with reference to firm attributes.

The paper is structured thus: section two is on literature review, section three is on the methodology, and section four is on presentation and discussion of results while section five is on conclusion and recommendation.

Literature Review

Earnings Quality

According to Richardson (2003), earnings quality is high when it can predict future earnings. Cohen (2003), Dechow and Dichev (2002) opine that quality of earnings is high when it is associated with the future operating cash flow. The above views see earnings quality from an accounting base perspective, i.e., earnings quality depends on accounting information only. In the same vein, Dechow and Schrand (2004) posit that earnings quality should reflect a firm's current operating performance and should be a good indicator for future operating performance. According to Richardson, Sloan, Soliman and Tuna (2001), earnings quality is appraised on the basis of stability of current earnings in relation to future earnings. Thus, implies that low earnings volatility indicates high earnings quality. According to Penman (2003), earnings have a high quality when it has the capacity to forecast future earnings. For the purpose of this research, the researcher construed earnings quality as the degree to which reported earnings capture a firm's economic reality.

How is earnings quality assessed?

Earnings quality is usually appraised from two broad classifications: accounting; and market based measures. According to Francis, LaFond and Schipper (2005), accounting measures depend on accounting information only while the market measures depend on market and accounting data. The accounting based classification measures are usually

referred to as reliability proxy while the market based classification measures usually referred to as the relevance proxy. According to Francis et al. (2006), accounting-based measures assigns assign cash flows to reporting periods through accruals while the market-based measures assume that the function of earnings is to reflect economic income as shown by stock returns. Examples of accounting measures are accrual quality, earnings persistency, earnings predictability, and earnings smoothness while market based measures are: accounting conservatism, timeliness, earnings response coefficient, value relevance etc. The above models have been used by severally researchers: for instance, accrual quality (Dechow & Dichev, 2002; Francis et al., 2005), earnings persistency (Penman & Zhang, 2002; Richardson et al., 2005), earnings predictability (Lipe, 1990), earnings smoothness (Leuz, Nanda & Wysocki, 2003), value relevance (Collins, Maydew & Weiss, 1997; Francis & Schipper, 1999), timeliness and accounting conservatism (e.g., Basu, 1997; Watts, 2003a; Bushman, Piotroski, & Smith, 2011).

Suffice to say that within these two broad approaches, there are a lot of varying measures to capture quality earnings such as discretionary accruals, earnings smoothness, earnings persistency and predictability, accounting conservatism, earnings response coefficient etc. This suggests that the earnings quality has varying importance to different stakeholders. According to Velury and Jenkins (2006), to rely on a single measure of earnings quality could lead to erroneous conclusion. These classifications suggest that earnings quality is multidimensional, consequently, no one measure fits all situations. For instance, if the research interest is associated with investors' perceptions of earnings, i.e. earnings quality to participants in the stock market, the appropriate measures to use are those which reflect stock prices and return (market based measures). Alternatively, if the interest is without reference to stock market participants, the direct measures becomes appropriate (accounting based measures). Therefore, prior studies on earnings quality indicator have opined that no proxy is superior for all decision models (Graham, Harvey, & Rajgopal, 2013; Singleton- Green, 2014). Therefore, it may be satirical to rely on a single measure, a combination of earnings quality measures could present a comprehensive framework from which earnings quality could be properly appraised. Prior extant literature seems to have enjoyed adequate attention on the use of accrual based measures, otherwise known as reliability measures unlike market base measures, otherwise known as relevance measures, to proxy earnings quality (Ball & Shivakumar, 2008; Cormier & Martinez, 2006; Dogan et al. 2007; Velury & Jenkins, 2006). From the foregoing, it is observed that earnings quality has different conceptualization, accounting versus market based approach.

Earnings quality can also be evaluated based on the qualitative characteristics of the International Accounting Standard Framework (IASB). These qualitative characteristics are the attributes that make the information provided in financial statements useful to users. According to the Framework, the decision usefulness of financial information are determined by the qualitative attributes of such information which are classified as: (i) fundamental; and (ii) enhancing. The former is further classified into relevance and faithful representation while the latter are enhancing are comparability, verifiability, timeliness and understandability. According to the Framework, financial information is relevant when it can influence a change in the decision making of its users, i.e. it can predict future outcome (predictive value) and can also provide a feedback about previous evaluation (confirmatory value). Financial information is faithfully represented when it is complete, neutral and free from error. This implies such information should represent the phenomena it purports to represent. The enhancing characteristics are only applied to confirm or enhance the quality of the information, they do not on their own enhance financial information quality. Another perspective to earnings quality is the market based approach. This approach sees earnings to be of a high quality when it can influence a company's stock in the stock market, i.e. when it has an association with the market return (K. Chan et al., 2006). These two perspectives of earnings quality implies that the relevance of earning quality could be seen from financial information user and investment perspectives. According to Schipper and Vincent (2003), earnings quality has a signaling effect for the efficient allocation of resources. Investors desired high financial quality because the value of their wealth is enhanced when resources are properly allocated unlike low quality earnings which is undesirable and could lead to misallocation of resources. From the financial information perspective, earnings quality is important for several reasons such as performance evaluation, executive compensation. However, it should be noted that opportunistic managers could overstate earnings quality in order to mask deteriorating solvency issues and this could mislead providers of resources.

Determinants of Earnings Quality

The determinants of earnings quality cut across corporate attributes, corporate governance audit quality etc. Studies have extensively addressed these determinants, however with emphasis on earnings management practice unlike on earnings quality. However, earnings management practice cannot be entirely severed from earnings quality being that high earning quality depicts low earnings management practices vice versa. Therefore, one advantage this study seems to have is in addressing these determinants in line with earnings quality. The study now proceed to examine selected firm attributes such as firm leverage, firm size, firm financial performance, and firm age.

Firm leverage and earnings quality

Leverage is the ratio of debt financing to total capital employed in an entity, which can either be short-term or long-term in nature. According to Prencipe (2004), firms with higher leverage levels incur more agency costs, and one way of reducing this cost and information asymmetries is to disclose more information. The relationship between leverage and earnings quality seems not to be clear in prior empirics, however most studies concluded that there exist an inverse relationship between both. Prior studies have investigated the impact of leverage on earnings quality. The study of DeAngelo, DeAngelo and Skinner (1994) examined the relationship between leverage and earnings quality and found that firms with high leverage exhibit low earnings quality. Shehu, (2009) examined the relationship between leverage and financial reporting quality and found that leverage exhibits a positive relationship with financial reporting quality. The study of Iman and Nejad (2015) examined the relationship between leverage and earnings management and found that leverage exhibits a positive relationship with earnings management. The study of Bassiouny, Soliman and Ragab (2016) investigated the relationship between selected firm specific attributes and earnings management of listed firms and found that leverage exhibit a positive relationship with earnings management. The study of Nelson and George (2013) examined some selected firm attributes and earnings management. The study found that highly levered firms engage in earnings management in order to attract more capital. Similarly, Obeidat (2016) examined earnings management and capital structure of twenty nine firms listed in Abi Dhabi Stock Exchange. The study revealed that financial leverage influence earnings management positively. Gombola, Ho and Huang (2016) examined the influence of liquidity and leverage on earnings management of commercial banks during the period 1999 to 2013. The study found that managers aggressively engage in earnings management practice as a positive relationship was found between it and leverage. The study of Uwuigbe, Ranti, and Bernard (2015) examined earnings management determinants among twenty companies. The study found no association between leverage and earnings management.

Firm size and earnings quality

The size of a company is often used as a germane characteristic of firms in prior studies. Studies have opined that firm size plays a major role in the disclosure requirement of companies (Roberts et al., 2005). According to Watts and Zimmerman (1986), firm size exhibits an inverse relationship with earnings quality, the reason being that due to regulatory scrutiny, larger firms often make income-decreasing accounting method choices. On the contrary, Ball and Foster (1982) examined the relationship between firm size and earnings quality and found that firm size exhibits a positive relationship with

earnings quality. Larger firms do incur fixed costs to maintain internal controls. Doyle, Ge and McVay (2007) opined that smaller firms would want to correct previous reported earnings due to deficiencies in internal control. The following are prior extant literatures that have examined this relationship: The study of Dwi Lusi (2013) on the relationship between firm attributes and earnings management among listed food and beverage companies in Indonesia. The study found that firm size exhibits a significant inverse relationship with earnings management. This suggests that larger firms tend to avoid earnings manipulation. Olowokure, Tanko and Nyor (2016) examined the relationship between selected firm attributes and financial reporting quality of banks quoted in the NSE. The study used data sourced from the audited annual report of the Deposit Money Banks during the period 2005 to 2014. The study found that firm size has no significant impact on financial reporting quality. The study of Mahboub (2017) investigated the relationship between selected firm attributes and reporting quality. The sample consists of twenty two (22) Lebanese banks during the period 2012 to 2015. The study found that size has no significant impact on financial reporting quality. Adebayo and Adebisi (2016) investigated firm characteristics and the timeliness of financial reporting of banks listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The sample consists of fifteen (15) banks during the period 2005 to 2013. The result showed that size exhibits significant impact on the timeliness of financial reporting. The study of Kenny and Luqman (2019) examined firm attributes and financial reporting quality among manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study deployed twenty five (25) sampled companies during the period 2009 to 2016. The study showed that firm size has a significant positive relationship with financial reporting quality.

2.6 Firm profit and earnings quality

Firm financial performance often surrogated using return on assets and return on equity has been widely used as determinants of reporting quality. It is the ability of managers to utilize resources at their disposal to generate earnings over a period of time. According to Haryono and Iskandar (2015), it shows the financial health of a firm over a period of time. According to Orlitzky et al. (2003), it takes different forms such as: organization internal efficiency (accounting measurement); shareholders satisfaction (market measurement); and subjective estimation of organization financial performance (survey measurement). The relationship between firm financial performance and quality reporting has been imprecise. For instance, Doyle et al. (2007) opined that firms could engage in earnings management due to weak performance. Kenny and Luqman (2019) examined selected firm attributes and the quality of financial reporting among manufacturing companies quoted in the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The sample consists of Twenty-five (25) companies during

the period 2009 to 2016. The quality of financial reporting was proxy using the modified Dechow and Dichev's (2002). The result showed that profitability exhibits positive significant relationship with reporting quality. Akhgar and Karami (2014) examined the relationship between firm specific attributes and reporting quality. The sample consist of one hundred and twenty active companies in Tehran Stock Exchange (TSE) during the period 1982 to 1991. The result revealed that profitability exhibits positive and significant on influencing financial reporting quality. Davidson, Stewart and Kent (2005) examined the relationship between firm characteristics and firm financial performance. They found that when profit is low, managers engages in the manipulation of accounting accruals. The study of Nelson and George (2013) examined firm characteristics and earnings management. The study found that firm performance exhibits an insignificant relationship between firm performance and earnings management. In the aforementioned study of Mahboub (2017), the determinants of financial reporting quality was examined. The sample consist of twenty two (22) banks listed in the Lebanese Stock Exchange during the period 2012 to 2015. The study found than profitability has insignificant impact on reporting quality among Lebanese banks.

Firm age and earnings quality

This refers to how old the firm is from the date of listing. According to Shumway (2001), firm age is the number of years from the date the company was listed. Firm age has been widely discussed in literature as a germane corporate attribute and a determinant of earnings management. One area of discourse on firm age has to do with the behavior of old and young firm in relations to earnings management practice. For instance, Elshabasy (2016) opines that older firms has the tendency not to manage earnings than younger firms, the reason being that older firms have a higher value in the market and reputation to protect. Also, it is believed that older firms have strong internal control to monitor earnings, consequently, would report higher quality of earnings. The relationship between firm age and earnings quality has been addressed in prior empiric, however with divergent findings. The study of Debnath (2017) examined earnings management among non-financial firms in Indian. The sample consist of 756 firm- year observations during the period 2007 to 2015. The study found that firm age exhibits a positive relationship with earnings management. In the aforementioned study of Olowokure et al. (2016) on the association between the structural attributes of firm and financial reporting quality among DMBs quoted in the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The sample consist of thirteen DMBs during the period 2005 to 2014. The findings revealed that firm age exhibits insignificant impact on the quality of financial reporting. Also, the study of Bassiouny et al. (2016) revealed that firm age exhibits insignificant relationship with earnings management. Alexander and

Hengky (2017) examined the determinants of earnings management in Indonesian stock exchange. The study found that firm age has no relationship with earnings management. The study of Echobu, Okika and Maliafa (2017) revealed that firm age exhibits significant positive relations with financial reporting quality. The study of Roychowdhury (2006) examined the determinants of earnings management practices. Using one thousand six hundred and eighty-seven firm year observations, the study found that firm age exhibits positive relationship with earnings manipulation. The study of Debnath (2017) examined earnings management practices among non-financial Indian firms. The study consist of 756 firm year observations during the period 2007 to 2015. The result revealed that firm age exhibits a positive relationship with earnings management.

Theoretical Review

Several theories have been used in earnings management studies such as opportunity theory, contracting theory, political cost theory, agency theory etc. However, the study is anchored on agency. The study now proceeds to discuss agency theory.

Agency Theory

Agency theory was propounded by Berle and Means (1932), however formalized by Jensen and Meckling (1976). Agency conflict arises due to ownership and control separation. Consequently, investors bear the ultimate cost or benefit of the decision made by managers. Although the separation of ownership from control presents some advantages such as the ability of ownership to change without impacting operation, the possibility of hiring expert to act as manager, however, it presents a much bigger challenge of wealth shifting from owners to agents. The agency theory analyses the contractual relationship that exist between company owners (shareholders), and its agents (management). According to Demsetz and Lehn (1985), the principal (shareholders) and the agent (managers) are assumed to follow their own interests. This implies that corporate resources may not be used entirely to increase shareholder value, rather for the benefits of corporate insiders. According to Holmstrom (1979) and Wilson (1968), moral hazard becomes the consequence associated with the inequitable distribution of information in the principal-agent relationship. In order to alleviate the negative consequences of this problem, agency theory describes the need for monitoring and contracting arrangements (Fama & Jensen, 1983; Jensen & Meckling, 1976). According to Shehata (2014), disclosing complete financial information devoid of misstatement through financial reporting helps mitigate the agency problem. Therefore, managers are expected, based on agency theory, to report appropriate, complete and adequate information to the business owners.

Methodology

The study used longitudinal research design. The longitudinal research design is suitable for panel study because it entails investigating a phenomenon over a period of time. In this case, the subject of investigation is the listed company over an eight year period (2014 to 2021). The thirteen Deposit Money Banks listed as at 31st December 2021 is the population of the study. The study choice DMBs because their annual report is readily available. The study took a census of the entire thirteen DMBs because the number is exhaustible. Also, an attempt to reduce the population will further reduce the observations count, consequently undermining the estimation result. Also, studying the entire thirteen DMBs will make for generalization of the study findings. The study made use of secondary data. The data is secondary because they are not in their raw form, i.e. the data has been subject to further processing by a third party. These data were sourced from the audited annual report of the sampled non-financial companies listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange as at 31st December, 2021.

Panel estimation technique will be suited for analyzing the data. The reason being that panel estimation takes into account the heterogeneity effect which is common in cross section study. By heterogeneity problem, we mean that these firms' specific variables contains confounding variables which are unobservable. These confounding variables may correlate with the stochastic term, consequently undermining the estimation result. In order to ascertain the significance of these features undermining the estimation result, random effect estimation is first conducted. If the hausman p-values of the random effect is less than the norm (5%), we say that the heterogeneity problem is significant to give concern, otherwise the result is satisfactory. When the heterogeneity effect gives a cause for concern, the estimation is done using mean-corrected values (FE). The FE estimates become reliable for making inferences for policy implication. Other tests that will be carried out are: (i) test for multicollinearity; (ii) test for equality of variance; (iii) test for model misspecification; and (iv) test for autocorrelation.

Model Specification

The study investigates firm characteristics and earnings quality listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) during the period to 2016 to 2021. Specifically, the variables of interest are firm leverage, firm size, firm profit and firm age. The model for this study is an adaptation of the study of Hassan and Farouk (2014). Hassan and Farouk (2014) examined firm attributes and earnings quality of listed Oil and Gas companies in Nigeria. In line with the agency theory, the model for this study is presented thus:

$$EQ=f(FL, FS, FP, FA) \text{-----}(i)$$

Where: EQ= Earnings quality; FL= Firm leverage; FS= Firm size; FP= Firm Profit; and FA = Firm age. The variable definition are given thus: For the FE, β_{1i} stands for the intercept of the entire thirteen DMBs, β_2 - β_5 = stands for the coefficient of the explanatory variables which are unknown, i stands for the number of companies, which is thirteen, t stands for the time which is eighteen years, μ_{it} = stochastic term.

Measurement of Variables

Table 1: Measurement of variables

No	Quantification	Source	Expected relationship
	Explained variable		
1	Earnings persistency, measured by the product of earnings retention rate and return on equity.	Perotti and Wagenhofer, 2014	Nil
	Independent variables		
2	It will be measured as the ratio of debt to total asset	Ullah and Kamal (2017)	+/-
3	It will be measured using the logarithm of firm total assets	Rahmawati (2013)	+
4	It will be measured by the ratio of profit after tax to total assets.	Hassan and Farouk (2014)	+/-
5	It will be measured using the number of years from the date of listing in the Nigerian Stock Exchange.	Aburime (2008)	+

Source: Researcher's compilation (2022)

Presentation and discussion of results

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	EQ	LEV	FS	FP	FA
Mean	-0.030	1.028	16.747	0.062	41.804
Max	4.368	19.557	21.595	6.174	98.000
Min	-15.611	0.032	10.955	-2.360	5.000
Std.	1.287	2.556	2.444	0.572	19.803
JB	104	108	5.843	431	4.872
Prob.	0.000	0.000	0.054	0.000	0.087
Obs.	189	189	189	189	189

Source: Researchers Computation (2022)

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics for the variables. As observed, EQ show the following statistics; Mean= -0.030, STD= 1.287 which is low and it indicates that EQ for the sampled firms exhibits a considerable clustering around the mean value, Max= 4.368 and Min= -15.611. LEV show the following statistics; Mean= 1.028, STD= 2.556 which is high and it indicates that LEV for the sampled firms exhibits a considerable level of dispersion from the mean value, Max= 19.557 and Min= 0.032. For FS, Mean= 16.747, STD= 2.444 which is low and it indicates that FS exhibits clustering around the mean value, Max= 21.595 and Min =10.955. For FP, Mean= 0.062, STD= 0.572 which is low and it indicates that FP for the sampled firms exhibits a considerable clustering around the mean value, Max= 6.174 and Min= -2.360. Finally, for FA, Mean= 41.804, STD= 19.803 which is low and it indicates that FA exhibits considerable clustering around the average, Max= 98.000 and Min= 5.000. The JB probability statistic values for most of the variables revealed the absence of normality. This is because the prob. JB value is greater than 0.05.

Table 3: Correlation Statistics

Correlation					
Probability	EQ	LEV	FS	FP	FA
EQ	1.000000				

LEV	-0.008835	1.000000			
	0.9040	-----			
FS	-0.013840	-0.390722	1.000000		
	0.8501	0.0000	-----		
FP	0.013943	0.102245	0.011330	1.000000	
	0.8490	0.1615	0.8770	-----	
FA	-0.001141	-0.119839	0.297380	-0.058383	1.000000
	0.9876	0.1005	0.0000	0.4249	-----

Source: Output from E-view 9 (2022).

From table 3 above, the correlation coefficients of the variables are examined. However, of particular interest to the study are the correlation between EQ and the respective firms' specific attributes such as firm size, firm profit, leverage, and firm age. As observed, EQ is positively correlated with FP ($r=0.014$), however insignificant relationship. On the contrary, EQ correlates with LEV ($r= -0.009$), FS ($r= -0.014$), and FA ($r= -0.001$), and are all statistically insignificant at 5%. A look at the inter-relationship among the explanatory variables shows the absence of the presence of multicollinearity. This is because the correlation coefficient among the variables did not exceed 0.8. However, this was further confirm using the multicollinearity test. We proceed to conduct the regression analysis as correlation analysis is not best suited for estimating causality between variables.

Table 4: Panel Regression Result

Variables	Random effec	Fixed effect
Dependent variable	: EQ	
C	0.537 (0.507)	0.762 (0.872)
LEV	-0.019 (0.637)	0.007 (0.962)
FS	-0.012 (0.776)	-0.052 (0.865)
FP	0.024 (0.888)	-0.008 (0.966)
FA	0.001 (0.933)	0.016 (0.794)
R ²	0.216	0.264
ADJ R ²	0.186	0.238
F-Stat	21.002 (0.000)	17.808 (0.000)
D.W	1.9	2.3
Hausman test:	0.585	

Source: Researchers Compilation (2023) using E-views 9. * & ** Significant at 10% & 5%

The study conducted a panel regression due to the heterogeneity problem associated with cross section study. There is the assumption that the unobserved effect in each of the cross sections will correlate with the error term. However, if the correlation between the unobserved term and the error term is significant to undermine regression estimation, the fixed effect estimation is conducted (FEM) which implies that the analysis is done based on mean corrected values, however if not significant, the random estimation (REM) result is accepted. The Hausman test p-value= 0.585 implies that the correlation between the unobserved variables and the error term is insignificant to undermine our estimation result, therefore the random effect estimation is accepted. The random effect estimation

revealed that the R^2 is 0.216 which suggests that the firm specific attributes 21.6% systematic variations in earnings quality with an adjusted value of 18.6%. The F-stat (21.002) and p-value (0.000) indicates that the hypothesis of a significant linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables cannot be rejected at 5% level while the D.W statistics of 1.9 indicates that the presence of serial correlation in the residuals is unlikely. However, this is further confirm further using breusch-godfrey serial correlation test.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of the result is based on the random effects estimation in table 4. The results are discussed below:

Firm Leverage and Earnings Quality

The results show that LEV exhibits a negative impact (-0.019) on earnings quality and statistically insignificant ($p=0.637$) at 5% level. This implies that an increase in LEV leads to 0.019 unit decrease in earnings quality. Based on the statistically insignificant criterion ($p=0.637>0.05$), we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_1) *that leverage does not have significant relationship with earnings quality among non-financial listed companies in Nigeria*. The findings is consistent with the study of Nelson and George (2013) examined some selected firm attributes and earnings management. The study found that highly levered firms engage in earnings management in order to attract more capital. Similarly, Obeidat (2016) examined earnings management and capital structure of twenty nine firms listed in Abi Dhabi Stock Exchange.

Firm Size and Earnings Quality

The results show that FS exhibits a negative impact (-0.012) on earnings quality, and it is statistically insignificant ($p=0.776$) at 5% level. This implies that an increase in FS will lead to a 0.012 unit decrease in earnings quality. Based on the statistically insignificant criterion ($p=0.776>0.05$), we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_1) *that firm size does not have significant relationship with earnings quality among non-financial listed companies in Nigeria*. The findings is consistent with the study of Dwi Lusi (2013) on the relationship between firm attributes and earnings management among listed food and beverage companies in Indonesia. The study found that firm size exhibits a significant inverse relationship with earnings management. This suggests that lagers firms tends to avoid earnings manipulation.

Firm Profit and Earnings Quality

The results show that ROA exhibits a positive impact (0.024) on earnings quality and is

statistically insignificant ($p=0.888$) at 5% level. This implies that an increase in ROA leads to a 0.024 unit increase in earnings quality. Based on the statistically insignificant criterion ($p=0.888>0.05$), we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_3) *that profit does not have significant relationship with earnings quality among non-financial listed companies in Nigeria*. The study is consistent with the findings of Kenny and Luqman (2019) examined selected firm attributes and the quality of financial reporting among manufacturing companies quoted in the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The sample consist of Twenty-five (25) companies during the period 2009 to 2016. The quality of financial reporting was proxy using the modified Dechow and Dichev's (2002). The result showed that profitability exhibits a positive significant relationship with reporting quality.

Firm Age and Earnings Quality

The results show that FA exhibits a positive impact (0.001) on earnings quality and it is statistically insignificant ($p=0.933$) at 5% level. This implies that an increase in FA leads to 0.001 increase in earnings quality. Based on the statistically insignificant criterion ($p=0.933>0.05$), we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_4) *that firm age does not have significant relationship with earnings quality among non-financial listed companies in Nigeria*. The study is consistent with the findings of Debnath (2017) examined earnings management among non-financial firms in Indian. The sample consist of 756 firm- year observations during the period 2007 to 2015. The study found that firm age exhibits a positive relationship with earnings management.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The broad objective of the study is to investigate firm characteristics and earnings quality among non-financial companies listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange during the period 2016 to 2021. The study was done due to the paucity of studies on earnings quality determinants unlike earnings management that has enjoyed much attention. Therefore, the study hypothesized that leverage, firm size, profitability and firm age have not significant relationship with earnings quality among non-financial companies listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Employing the panel regression estimation technique, the study finds that leverage, firm size, profitability, and firm has exhibit insignificant impact on earnings quality, however with differing nature of relationship. From the findings of the study, the study conclude that impact of leverage, firm size, profitability, and firm age on earnings quality is weak. This is because the joint explanation of 21.6% of the systematic variation on earnings quality is low. This suggests that earnings quality could be impacted by other determinants not accounted for in this study.

From the findings of the study, the study recommends that:

- (i) leverage exhibits inverse insignificant impact on earnings quality, firms should endeavour to strike an optimum capital structure mix that will optimum the value of the firm;
- (ii) although firm size exhibits inverse insignificant impact on earnings quality, firms should endeavour to maintain earnings quality, especially large firms as this tends to enhance and protect their reputation;
- (iii) profitability exhibits positive relationship, both profitable and unprofitable firms should maintain earnings quality in order to provide quality information to its numerous stakeholders; and
- (iv) firm age exhibits positive significant relationship with earnings quality, firms should continue to disclose more in order to protect their reputation and enhance their image.

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